

Disclaimer

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Goal of Tool

A key aspect of Responsible Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the ability to assess (and later mitigate) certain risks associated with the use of AI.

The AI Privacy Risk Assessment tool is aimed to help organizations developing ML models trained on people's personal and/or health data, especially those that need to be deployed outside of the organization or shared with third parties, to perform a privacy risk assessment of their AI models.

Assessing the privacy risk of machine learning (ML) models is crucial to enable wellinformed decision-making about whether to use a model in production, share it with third parties, or deploy it on customers' premises. Performing such an assessment can prevent organizations from releasing models that contain known privacy vulnerabilities and put at risk the privacy of the people whose data was used in training these models. In case of a privacy risk being detected, the tool also recommends privacy mitigation measures that can be applied to reduce this risk.

Tool description

The AI Privacy Risk Assessment (AIRA) tool is an end-to-end framework for privacy risk assessment of AI models. It aims to alleviate the issues of existing tools and frameworks that require a high degree of expertise or are tightly coupled with specific ML frameworks.

The tool enables assessing models from different ML frameworks, using a variety of different privacy attack and metric implementations, without requiring deep technical expertise.

The tool automates many of the decisions around which attacks and metrics to run, and takes care of all the technical preparation required to run them. It also summarizes the

individual attack results into an overall privacy risk score that is understandable by nontechnical users.

The tool is implemented as a python package, which can also be installed as a dev container that already includes all the required dependencies, thus making the installation easier and more user-friendly.

Installation

There are two possible ways to install and use the tool: as standalone python package or as dev container in VSCode.

As standalone python package:

Need to use a compatible python version. The package was tested with the following versions: 3.8.10 3.8.16

3.9.22

3.10.11

Install package requirements:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Depending on the ML framework used, some of the dependencies in `requirements_frameworks.txt` should also be installed (for example keras or pytorch). To run the tests, in addition the dependencies in `requirements_test.txt` should also be installed.

As dev container:

Install VSCode with dev containers extension.

Open top directory (*nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-devcontainer*). This directory should contain two sub-directories: *nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-toolkit* and *.devcontainer*.

Build and run container.

Add the current project package to the python path inside the container terminal:

```
export PYTHONPATH="${PYTHONPATH}:/workspaces/nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluationdevcontainer/nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-toolkit"
```

Run assessment in container terminal:

```
cd nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-toolkit/examples/pdn (or whatever folder your run_assessment.py and data is in).
```

```
python /usr/local/bin/python /workspaces/nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-devcontainer/nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-toolkit/examples/pdn/run_assessment.py
```

Run tests from command line (in container terminal):

```
cd nemecys-privacy-risk-evaluation-toolkit/ python  
-m unittest tests/metric/XXX.py
```

Usage

The main class to use when creating a model assessment is *PrivacyRiskMetric*. It contains two main methods: the `train()` method creates and initializes the assessment, and the `run()` method runs it.

The train method must be provided with two types of inputs:

1. Inputs regarding the target model to be assessed. This includes:
 - a. Either the target model itself, wrapped as a `UserModelInterface` object instance (`target_model` param), or information about the model's type such that a surrogate (shadow) model can be created, also wrapped as a `UserModelInterface` object (`shadow_model` param).
Alternatively, if a model object cannot be provided, the model's predictions on the train and test dataset may instead be provided to the `run()` method. To create a `UserModelInterface` instance, it must be provided a python instance of the trained/fitted model for assessment, for example a fitted `sklearn.linear_model.LogisticRegression()` object, and method name for getting predictions from the provided model object (`run_func` parameter).
 - b. The type of output the target model generates, as a `ModelOutputType` object. Possible values are:
 - i. `CLASSIFIER_PROBABILITIES` - vector of probabilities for a classification model
 - ii. `CLASSIFIER_LOGITS` - vector of logits for a classification model
 - iii. `CLASSIFIER_SCALAR` - label only for a classification model
 - iv. `REGRESSOR_SCALAR` - value for a regression model
 - v. `TIMESERIES` - vector of values
 - c. In case of a pytorch model, the following two must also be supplied:
 - i. `pytorch_loss` - a `torch.nn.modules.loss._Loss` object.
 - ii. `pytorch_optimizer` - a `torch.optim.Optimizer` object.
 - d. In case of a regression model, the following may be supplied:
 - i. `loss_fn` - a `Callable` that computes the loss function of the model. If not supplied, MSE loss will be used by default.
 - e. `blackbox_access` param - a Boolean indicating whether the real access to the model (when in production) is to the model outputs alone or also to the model internals.
 - f. `unlimited_queries` param - if `blackbox_access` is True, this is a Boolean indicating whether, in production, a user has unlimited access to query the model or the number of queries is restricted.
2. Inputs regarding the data that is input to the model. This includes:
 - a. The type of the input data to the model, as a `ModalityType` object (`data_type` param). Possible values are:
 - i. `TABULAR` - for tabular (numerical or categorical) data

- ii. `TIMESERIES` – for (multi-dimensional) time series data
- b. The input shape of the one sample of the input data, as a tuple (`input_shape` param). For example (1, 100, 3) or (4,).
- c. The number of output classes in case of a classification model (`nb_classes` param). If not a classification model, should be None.
- d. The dimensions of the output for time-series data (`output_shape` param).

Additional optional parameters can be used to determine the level and location of logging of the run (`log_path` and `log_level`) and information to be included in the result file for documentation purposes (`model_description`, `model_framework_version`, `python_version`).

The method returns an initialized *PrivacyRiskMetric* object, which can later be run.

Full method signature:

```

def train(
    cls,
    output_type:
ModelOutputType,
    input_shape: Tuple[int, ...] =
None,
    output_shape: Tuple[int, ...] = None,
nb_classes: int = None,
    target_model:
UserModelInterface = None,
    shadow_model:
UserModelInterface = None,
    data_type:
ModalityType = ModalityType.TABULAR,
blackbox_access: bool = True,
unlimited_queries: bool = True,
    loss_fn:
Callable = None,
    pytorch_loss: "torch.nn.modules.loss._Loss" = None,
pytorch_optimizer: "torch.optim.Optimizer" = None,
model_description: str = None,
model_framework_version: str = None,
python_version: str = None,
    log_path: str = None,
log_level: LogLevel = None
    ) -> PrivacyRiskMetric:
    """
    Method for preparing internal model representation and associated metadata.
    if
TIMESERIES:
input:
    output_shape,
output_type=ModelOutputType.TIMESERIES,
data_type=ModalityType.TIMESERIES,

    Args:
        output_type:
ModelOutputType
            The type of output the target model generates. One of:
CLASSIFIER_PROBABILITIES, CLASSIFIER_LOGITS,
CLASSIFIER_SCALAR or REGRESSOR_SCALAR.
        input_shape: Tuple[int, ...] or None if TIMESERIES
            Shape of one input sample as expected by the model, e.g.
input_shape=(1, 100, 3), input_shape=(4, )
        output_shape: Tuple[int, ...]
            Shape of one output sample predicted by the model, e.g.
output_shape=(1, 5, 3). In this version
only output_shape of (1,1,1) is supported.
        nb_classes: Union[int, None]
            The number of classes of the model. None for regressor, otherwise must
be provided.
        target_model: UserModelInterface
            The target model to assess. Must be already trained. If not supplied,
the assessment will be based

```

on the supplied data and shadow models. The model should return predictions through the `run` method.

`shadow_model: UserModelInterface`
A model to be used as a template for generating shadow models. This is needed in case some of the data needed for normal model assessment is missing, such as a target model object or training data.

For simple models such as sklearn models, it is enough to supply the `user_model_class` which can be instantiated and trained. For more complex models such as pytorch or keras models or sklearn pipelines, an untrained model instance must be provided. The model should return predictions through the `run` method.

The model should be fitted through the `train` method.

`data_type: ModalityType`
The type of the data. Default is TABULAR.

`blackbox_access: bool`
Boolean describing the type of deployment of the model (when in production). Set to True if the model is only available via query (API) access, i.e., only the outputs of the model are exposed, and False if the model internals are also available. Default is True.

`unlimited_queries: bool`
If `black_box_access` is True, this boolean indicates whether a user can perform unlimited queries to the model API or whether there is a limit to the number of queries that can be submitted.

Default is True.

`loss_fn: Callable`
Function that takes in two `np.ndarray`s, of true values and predicted values, and returns the loss value for each pair. May be supplied for blackbox regression models (when only a predict method is provided). Default is MSE loss.

`pytorch_loss: _Loss`
Required for pytorch models, the loss function used for training.

`pytorch_optimizer: Optimizer`
Required for pytorch models, the optimizer used for training.

`model_description: str`
Description of the model. Optional.

`model_framework_version: str`
The version of the model framework. Optional.

`python_version: str`
The python version required for the model. Optional.

`log_path: str`
Path location for the log file. If not provided log will be written to the console. Optional.

`log_level: LogLevel enum`

```
        The log level. If not provided 'error' is used. Possible values are:
off, fatal, error, warning, info, trace, debug, debug1, debug2,
debug3, debug4.
```

```
        See https://github.com/IBM/alchemy-logging#channels-and-levels.
```

```
Optional.
```

```
        Returns:
```

```
privacy_risk_metric.privacy_risk_main_metric.PrivacyRiskMetric
    Instantiated PrivacyRiskMetric.
```

```
"""
```

Examples of instantiating a Privacy Risk Metric using the train method:

Model instance is available sklearn classifier model:

```
target_model = UserModelInterface(user_model=user_model, run_func="predict_proba")
privacy_risk_metric = PrivacyRiskMetric.train(target_model=target_model,
                                             output_type=ModelOutputType.CLASSIFIER_PROBABILITIES,
                                             input_shape=x_train.shape[1:],
                                             nb_classes=get_nb_classes(y_test))
```

Model instance is available, sklearn regression model:

```
target_model = UserModelInterface(user_model=user_model, run_func="predict")
privacy_risk_metric = PrivacyRiskMetric.train(target_model=target_model,
                                             output_type=ModelOutputType.REGRESSOR_SCALAR,
                                             input_shape=x_train.shape[1:],
                                             nb_classes=get_nb_classes(y_test))
```

Time-series model, no model instance, prediction data is provided:

```
ts_y_test, ts_y_train, ts_pred_test, ts_pred_train =
get_user_input_from_ts(data_base_path, num_of_samples)
```

```
privacy_risk_metric = PrivacyRiskMetric.train(
output_type=ModelOutputType.TIMESERIES,
output_shape=ts_y_test.shape, data_type=ModalityType.TIMESERIES,
)
```

The run method must be provided with two types of inputs:

1. Data to run the assessment with. This includes:
 - a. Test data (optional):
 - i. Input data/features to the model (`test_data`). Can be provided as a numpy ndarray or a pandas DataFrame.
 - ii. Target true labels (`test_targets`). Can be provided as a numpy ndarray or a pandas DataFrame or Series.
 - iii. Model predictions for the test input data (`test_predictions`) – may be provided in cases where the target model itself was not

provided in the 'train' method. Can be provided as a numpy ndarray or a pandas DataFrame or Series.

- b. Training data of the target model, if available (optional). This must be the same (or a subset of) data that was used to train the target model:
 - i. Input data/features to the model (`train_data`). Can be provided as a numpy ndarray or a pandas DataFrame.
 - ii. Target true labels (`train_targets`). Can be provided as a numpy ndarray or a pandas DataFrame or Series.
 - iii. Model predictions for the training input data (`train_predictions`) – may be provided in cases where the target model itself was not provided in the 'train' method. Can be provided as a numpy ndarray or a pandas DataFrame or Series.

Either test data or training data must be provided (best results are achieved when providing both).

2. Configuration information for running the assessment:

- a. A list of features to attack when applying attribute inference (`features_to_attack` param). These should be features that represent sensitive/personal information. Provided as a list of `AttackedFeature` objects. Each `AttackedFeature` must contain an index or slice indicating the column(s) that represent this feature (`ind_or_slice` param), and optionally a feature name (`name` param) and a map of feature values to names (for categorical features) (`map_values_to_names` param). Each feature must also indicate whether it is numeric or not (i.e., string values) (`is_numeric` param), default is True, and whether it is a continuous feature (`is_continuous` param), default is False.
If none are provided, the assessment will not include attribute inference attacks.
- b. The number of times to run each attack (`num_attack_runs` param) – The higher this number, the more stable the results will be, however it also entails a linear increase in run time. Recommended is 5-10. Default value is 1.
- c. The way to aggregate scores across runs and attacks, as a `ScoreAggregationMode` object (`score_aggregation_mode` param). Possible values are: `AVERAGE` and `WORST`. Default is `ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE`.
- d. A random seed for the data splits performed within the assessment process (`seed` param). Used to enable reproducibility. Note that some of the attacks themselves are non-deterministic and are not currently controlled by this seed.
- e. The mode in which to run the workflow (`run_mode` param) as a `RunModeType` object. Possible values are:
 - i. `DRY_RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT` – Evaluate which privacy attacks/metrics may be run against the model according to the given model, data

and configuration and return the list of attacks/metrics that can be run. Does not actually run them.

- ii. `DRY_RUN_DATA_ASSESSMENT` - Evaluate which privacy attacks/metrics may be run against the input data only according to the given data and configuration and return the list of attacks/metrics that can be run. Does not actually run them.
- iii. `RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT` – Runs all possible privacy attacks/metrics that may be run against the model according to the given model, data and configuration and return the list of attacks/metrics that were run and their results.
- iv. `RUN_DATA_ASSESSMENT` - Runs all possible privacy attacks/metrics that may be run against the input data only according to the given data and configuration and return the list of attacks/metrics that were run and their results.

Currently only `RunModeType.RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT` and `RunModeType.DRY_RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT` are supported and `RunModeType.RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT` is the default.

- f. A list of underlying risk frameworks to use to run attacks (`risk_frameworks_to_use` param). Provided as a set of `RiskFramework` objects. Currently only `RiskFramework.ART` is supported.
- g. A list of attack families to run (`attack_families_to_run` param). Provided as a set of `RiskObjectFamily` objects. Currently only `RiskObjectFamily.ATTRIBUTE_INFERENCE` and `RiskObjectFamily.MEMBERSHIP` are supported and are both in the default list.
- h. A Boolean indicating whether to generate shadow models in the assessment, if relevant (`run_shadow` param). Default is True. Additional optional parameters can be used to be included in the result file for documentation purposes (`project_name`).

The run method returns a `RiskAssessmentReport` object, which can be exported to a json file. It may be run multiple times on a single `PrivacyRiskMetric` object, possibly on different datasets and/or with different configurations.

Full method signature:

```
def run(
    self,
    test_data:
    Union[np.ndarray, pd.DataFrame] = None,
    test_targets: Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame] = None,
    test_predictions: Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame] = None,
    train_data: Union[np.ndarray, pd.DataFrame] = None,
    train_targets:
    Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame] = None,
    train_predictions:
    Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame] = None,
    features_to_attack: List[AttackedFeature] = None,
    num_attack_runs:
    int = 1,
    score_aggregation_mode: ScoreAggregationMode =
    ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE,
    seed: int = None,
    run_mode: RunModeType = RunModeType.RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT,
    risk_frameworks_to_use: Set[RiskFramework] = None,
```

```

        attack_families_to_run: Set[RiskObjectFamily] = None,
run_shadow: bool = True,                project_name: str = None

    ) -> RiskAssessmentReport:
        """
        Method that runs the assessment. Evaluates which specific metrics can be run
        based on the provided inputs,
        runs them and summarizes the results. If running in elicitation mode, only the
        first part is performed without actually running the metrics.
        Currently, only numeric data is supported.
        if
TIMESERIES
input:
    test_targets
test_predictions
train_targets
train_predictions
    Expected Data with the following dimensions: (num_of_samples,
num_of_time_stamps, num_of_variables)

output:
    json file to: '../resources/outputs'

    Args:
        test_data: Union[np.ndarray, pd.DataFrame] or None if TIMESERIES
            Test data features, optional. At least one of test_data or train_data
must be provided.
        test_targets: Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame]
            Test data true labels, optional. Values should be numerical.
        test_predictions: Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame]
            Predictions of the target model on the test data, optional. Values should
be numerical.
        train_data: Union[np.ndarray, pd.DataFrame] or None if TIMESERIES
            Training data features. This must be the same (or a subset of) data that was used
to train the target model, optional. At least one of test_data or
train_data must be provided.
        train_targets: Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame]
            Training data true labels, optional. Values should be numerical.
        train_predictions: Union[np.ndarray, pd.Series, pd.DataFrame]
            Predictions of the target model on the training data, optional. Values
should be numerical.
        features_to_attack:
            A list of AttackedFeature objects, one for each feature (attribute)
that should be attacked when applying attribute inference. These
should be features that represent personal information, are categorical and

```

```

        have a relatively small number of categories. If none are supplied,
the assessment will not include attribute inference.
        or None if TIMESERIES
num_attack_runs: int
        The number of times to run each attack. For score_aggregation_mode
AVERAGE, it helps to stabilize the
        results. For score_aggregation_mode WORST, it increases the chances of
finding a privacy risk if such exists.
        Default is 1. The higher the number, the longer it takes for risk
assessment to run.
        score_aggregation_mode: ScoreAggregationMode
        The manner in which to aggregate results from multiple runs/attacks.
Should be one of AVERAGE or WORST. Default is AVERAGE.
        seed: int
        The seed to use for the random number generator used in splitting the
data, optional.
        run_mode: RunModeType
        Whether to run the full risk assessment (RUN_XXX) or only do dry-run
(DRY_RUN_XXX),
        i.e. return which possible attacks can be run , either on the data or
the model.
        Default is RUN_MODEL_ASSESSMENT (to run a full risk assessment on the
model)
        risk_frameworks_to_use: Set[RiskFramework]
        The set of underlying risk (attack) frameworks to use in the
assessment. Currently, only ART is supported.
        attack_families_to_run: Set[RiskObjectFamily]
        The set of attack families to run in the assessment, optional. Default
is to run all possible families.
        run_shadow: bool
        A boolean indicating whether to run attacks in "shadow mode" if
running them on the target model is not
        possible. Default is True. For non-numeric data, currently only shadow
model scikitlearn Pipeline instance is supported.
        project_name: str
        Name for this evaluation project. This name is included in the final
report.

    Returns:
trust_art_privacy_ext.data_model.privacy_workflow_result.PrivacyRiskMetricResult
Instantiated PrivacyRiskMetricResult. Privacy Risk Assessment "run" or
"dry-run" result.
"""

```

Examples of running a Privacy Risk Metric using the run method:

Both training and test data available, there are features to attack:

```
features_to_attack = [
    AttackedFeature(slice(21,23), "Social"),
    AttackedFeature(slice(19,21), "finance")]

result = privacy_risk_metric.run(test_data=x_test,
                                test_targets=y_test,
                                train_data=x_train,
                                train_targets=y_train,
                                features_to_attack=features_to_attack,
                                score_aggregation_mode=ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE,
                                num_attack_runs=3)
```

Both training and test data available, there are features to attack, some are nonnumeric:

```
features_to_attack = [
    AttackedFeature(slice(21,23), "Social"),
    AttackedFeature(slice(19,21), "finance")]

result = privacy_risk_metric.run(test_data=x_test,
                                test_targets=y_test,
                                train_data=x_train,
                                train_targets=y_train,
                                features_to_attack=features_to_attack,
                                score_aggregation_mode=ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE,
                                num_attack_runs=3)
```

Both training and test data available, no features to attack:

```
result = privacy_risk_metric.run(test_data=x_test,
                                test_targets=y_test,
                                train_data=x_train,
                                train_targets=y_train,
                                score_aggregation_mode=ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE,
                                num_attack_runs=3)
```

Both training and test data available, there are features to attack, only run attribute family:

```
features_to_attack = [AttackedFeature(slice(21,23), "Social"), AttackedFeature(slice(19,21), "finance")]

result = privacy_risk_metric.run(test_data=x_test,
                                test_targets=y_test,
                                train_data=x_train,
                                train_targets=y_train,
                                features_to_attack=features_to_attack,
                                score_aggregation_mode=ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE,
                                num_attack_runs=3,
                                attack_families_to_run={RiskObjectFamily.ATTRIBUTE_INFERENCE})
```

Time-series data, no features to attack:

```
result = privacy_risk_metric.run(test_targets=ts_y_test,
```

```
test_predictions=ts_pred_test,  
train_targets=ts_y_train, train_predictions=ts_pred_train)
```

Example code for running a model assessment can be found in the *examples/pdn/run_assessment.py* file.

For this file to be able to run, the data and models that will be used in the assessment should also be copied to this folder, and the paths in the *run_assessment.py* file updated accordingly.

See below a full example of creating and running the *PrivacyRiskMetric* and exporting its result to json:

```
from privacy_risk_metric.config.attacked_feature import AttackedFeature  
from privacy_risk_metric.model.user_model_interface import UserModelInterface  
from privacy_risk_metric.privacy_risk_metric import PrivacyRiskMetric  
from privacy_risk_metric.types import ModelOutputType, ScoreAggregationMode, RunModeType, RiskObjectFamily  
from privacy_risk_metric.utils.utils import get_nb_classes  
  
input_shape = x_train.shape[1:]  
nb_classes = get_nb_classes(y_test)  
  
# Create the parameters for train/run and invoke them  
target_model = UserModelInterface(user_model=user_model, run_func="predict_proba")  
privacy_risk_metric = PrivacyRiskMetric.train(target_model=target_model,  
                                              output_type=ModelOutputType.CLASSIFIER_PROBABILITIES,  
                                              input_shape=input_shape,  
                                              nb_classes=nb_classes)  
  
print("Privacy Metric Training - done")  
  
features_to_attack = [AttackedFeature(slice(21,23), "Social"), AttackedFeature(slice(19,21), "finance")]  
  
result = privacy_risk_metric.run(test_data=x_test,  
                               test_targets=y_test,  
                               train_data=x_train,  
                               train_targets=y_train,  
                               features_to_attack=features_to_attack,  
                               score_aggregation_mode=ScoreAggregationMode.AVERAGE,  
                               num_attack_runs=3)  
  
print("Result:")  
print(result.to_json(indent=4, sort_keys=False))
```

Results

The output json contains two main parts:

1. General information about the assessment. This includes information about the assessed model and datasets used, the input configuration parameters supplied by the user, dates and time of creating and completing the assessment, status of the assessment, which attacks were run, etc.
2. Results of the assessment. This includes both overall privacy health scores, which are the combined privacy results across all the attacks that were run, aggregated and normalized such that higher scores mean better privacy (between 0-1), and detailed (raw) attack results.

The single overall privacy health score is **accuracy_health_score**. The raw results are grouped by attack family and also aggregated and normalized between different attack runs within the family. In this section, higher scores mean worse privacy.

In the json, each field comes with a corresponding description field that explains what the field means. So, the result is mostly self-explanatory.

Full json example:

```
{
  "id_description": "An auto-generated ID of this specific assessment",
  "id": "job:c46ede6514924b84893ec3922885953b",
  "project_id_description": "An auto-generated ID of the project in which the assessment was run",
  "project_id": "project:3fb315fe3dcb4f54a05058dfe29fa38d",
  "number_of_runs_description": "The number of times each attack was run within the assessment",
  "number_of_runs": 1,
  "run_shadow": true,
  "attack_families": [
    "MEMBERSHIP",
    "ATTRIBUTE_INFERENCE"
  ],
  "risk_frameworks": [
    "ART"
  ],
  "assessment_id_description": "An auto-generated ID of this specific assessment run",
  "assessment_id": "assessment:715d4169a6d64c2bbddb696f928fd5d",
  "created_date_description": "The date and time when the assessment was created",
  "created_date": "2025-05-27T13:43:11.782306+00:00",
  "started_date_description": "The date and time when the assessment was started",
  "started_date": "2025-05-27T13:43:11.782371+00:00",
  "completed_date_description": "The date and time when the assessment was completed",
  "completed_date": "2025-05-27T13:43:44.735169+00:00",
}
```

```

"created_by_description": "The name of the tool/service running the assessment",
"created_by": "IBM-ai-privacy-risk-toolkit",
"status_description": "Whether the assessment failed or succeeded",
"status": "success",
"mode_description": "Whether this was an actual assessment or a dry-run (dry-run only
returns the attacks to be applied in the assessment but does not actually run them)",
"mode": "assessment",
"model": {
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  "file_description": "The name of the file from which the model was loaded, if relevant",
  "file": {},
  "config": {
    "python_version_description": "The python version used to train the model",
    "python_version": "3.9.22",
    "framework_type_description": "The ML framework used to train the model (e.g.,
scikitlean, pytorch, etc.)",
    "framework_type": "scikit_learn",
    "framework_version_description": "The version of the ML framework used to train the
model",
    "access_description": "The type of access defined for the assessed model (e.g., blackbox or
whitebox access)",
    "access": "blackbox",
    "queries_limited_description": "A boolean describing whether the number of user queries
to the model is limited or not",
    "queries_limited": false,
    "model_type_description": "The way in which the model was supplied for the assessment
(e.g., trained model object, API, etc.)",
    "model_type": "trained_model_object",
    "algorithm_description": "The type of ML model being assessed (e.g., classification,
regression, etc.)",
    "algorithm": "classification",
    "output_format_description": "The format of the model output (e.g., classifier
probabilities, time series, etc.)",
    "output_format": "Classifier probabilities"
  }
},
"data": {
  "sensitive_attributes_description": "The list of sensitive attributes selected to perform
attribute inference against",
  "sensitive_attributes": [
    "MeanHR:numeric",
    "MeanRR:numeric"
  ],
  "input_shape_description": "The input shape of the data",
  "input_shape": "(2,)",

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    "num_of_classes_description": "The number of output label classes (for a classification
model)",
    "num_of_classes": 5,
    "x_train_description": "Whether the training input data was provided for assessment ",
    "x_train": true,
    "y_train_description": "Whether the training data true labels were provided for assessment
",
    "y_train": true,
    "y_pred_train_description": "Whether the model predictions for the training data were
provided for assessment ",
    "y_pred_train": false,
    "x_test_description": "Whether the test input data was provided for assessment ",
    "x_test": true,
    "y_test_description": "Whether the test data true labels were provided for assessment ",
    "y_test": true,
    "y_pred_test_description": "Whether the model predictions for the test data were provided
for assessment ",
    "y_pred_test": false,
    "output_shape_description": "The output shape of the data (true labels as well as model
predictions)"
},
"result": {
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"privacy": {
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accuracy_health_score and normalized to be between 0-100. The higher this score is, the better
the privacy of the assessed model.",
            "aggregate": 55.0,
            "attack_families_description": "Assessment results per attack family",
"attack_families": [
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Inference)",
                    "name": "Membership",
                    "attacks_description": "The specific attack implementations that were run within
each family",
                    "attacks": [
                        {
                            "name_description": "The name of the attack implementation",
                            "name": "MembershipInferenceBlackBox",
                            "attacked_model_description": "Which target model was used in this attack,
i.e., whether it was the original model or a shadow model built with either the training or test
data supplied",

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    "attacked_model": "Original",
    "framework_description": "The attack framework from which the attack
implementation was taken",
    "framework": "ART"
  }
],
  "risk_scores_description": "All risk scores represent privacy risk, i.e., the higher
the score the higher the risk (the worse the privacy). All scores are between 0-1.",
  "risk_scores": {
    "accuracy_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated accuracy
scores of the attacks run in this family",
    "accuracy_risk_score": 0.86,
    "precision_risk_score": 0.88,
    "precision_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated precision
scores of the attacks run in this family",
    "recall_risk_score": 0.82,
    "recall_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated recall
scores of the attacks run in this family",
    "f1_risk_score": 0.85,
    "f1_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated f1 scores of the
attacks run in this family",
    "attribute_scores_description": "Risk scores per attribute/feature that is the
target of the attack (for membership inference there is always only one attribute called
membership)",
    "attribute_scores": [
      {
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        "feature_name": "Membership",
        "accuracy_description": "The accuracy scores of the attack on this
feature",
        "accuracy": {
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          "average_run_description": "The average attack accuracy across all
runs",
          "average_run": 0.93,
          "std_dev_run_description": "The standard deviation of the attack
accuracy across all runs",
          "std_dev_run": 0.0,
          "ideal_range_description": "The ideal range of the accuracy score (that
represents perfect privacy)",
          "ideal_range": {
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            "minimum": 0.0,

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    "maximum_description": "The maximum value of the ideal range",
"maximum": 0.5
  }
},
"values": [
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    "value_description": "The feature value that is the target of the
attack (for membership inference there is always only one value called \"1\" that represents
members)",
    "value": {
      "id_description": "The actual value of the attacked feature",
"text": "[1.]"
    },
    "precision_description": "The precision scores of the attack",
"precision": {
      "worst_run_description": "The worst attack accuracy across all
runs",
      "worst_run": 0.94,
      "average_run_description": "The average attack accuracy across
all runs",
      "average_run": 0.94,
      "std_dev_run_description": "The standard deviation of the attack
accuracy across all runs",
      "std_dev_run": 0.0,
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(that represents perfect privacy)",
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        "minimum": 0.0,
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range",
        "maximum": 0.5
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    },
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"recall": {
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runs",
      "worst_run": 0.91,
      "average_run_description": "The average attack accuracy across
all runs",
      "average_run": 0.91,
      "std_dev_run_description": "The standard deviation of the attack
accuracy across all runs",

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(that represents perfect privacy)",
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range",
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runs",
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        "average_run_description": "The average attack accuracy across
all runs",
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        "std_dev_run_description": "The standard deviation of the attack
accuracy across all runs",
        "std_dev_run": 0.0,
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(that represents perfect privacy)",
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            "minimum": 0.0,
            "maximum_description": "The maximum value of the ideal
range",
            "maximum": 0.5
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    },
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characteristic curve of the attack",
    "roc": {
        "auc_roc_description": "The area under the roc curve",
        "auc_roc": {
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runs",
            "worst_run": 0.98,
            "average_run_description": "The average attack accuracy across
all runs",

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    "average_run": 0.98,
    "std_dev_run_description": "The standard deviation of the attack
accuracy across all runs",
    "std_dev_run": 0.0,
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score (that represents perfect privacy)",
    "ideal_range": {
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range",
        "minimum": 0.0,
        "maximum_description": "The maximum value of the ideal
range",
        "maximum": 0.5
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},
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of the attack",
    "false_positive_rates": [
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        0.0,
        0.0,
        0.048,
        0.072,
        0.136,
        0.136,
        0.224,
        0.384,
        0.408,
        0.408,
        0.408,
        0.408,
        1.0
    ],
    "true_positive_rates_description": "A vector of the true positive
rates corresponding to the false positive rates",
    "true_positive_rates": [
        0.72,
        0.72,
        0.808,
        0.968,
        0.976,

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0.984,
                                0.976,
                                0.992,
                                1.0,
                                1.0,
1.0,
                                1.0,
                                1.0,
                                1.0
                                ]
                                }
                                }
],
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attribute/feature",
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  "precision_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated
precision scores of the values of this feature",
  "recall_risk_score": 0.82,
  "recall_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated recall
scores of the values of this feature",
  "f1_risk_score": 0.85,
  "f1_risk_score_description": "Risk score based on aggregated f1 scores of
the values of this feature"
}
]
}
},
{
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Inference)",
  "name": "Attribute Inference",
  "attacks_description": "The specific attack implementations that were run within
each family",
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i.e., whether it was the original model or a shadow model built with either the training or test
data supplied",
      "attacked_model": "Original",
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implementation was taken",

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    "framework": "ART"
  },
  {
    "name_description": "The name of the attack implementation",
    "name": "AttributeInferenceMembership",
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i.e., whether it was the original model or a shadow model built with either the training or test
data supplied",
    "attacked_model": "Original",
    "framework_description": "The attack framework from which the attack
implementation was taken",
    "framework": "ART"
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],
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the score the higher the risk (the worse the privacy). All scores are between 0-1.",
  "risk_scores": {
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scores of the attacks run in this family",
    "accuracy_risk_score": 0.12,
    "attribute_scores_description": "Risk scores per attribute/feature that is the
target of the attack (for membership inference there is always only one attribute called
membership)",
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        "feature_name": "MeanHR",
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feature",
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          "worst_run": 0.12,
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runs",
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accuracy across all runs",
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represents perfect privacy)",
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            "maximum_description": "The maximum value of the ideal range",

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        "maximum": 0.0
    }
}
},
{
    "feature_name_description": "The name of the attacked feature",
    "feature_name": "MeanRR",
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feature",
    "accuracy": {
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        "average_run_description": "The average attack accuracy across all
runs",
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        "std_dev_run_description": "The standard deviation of the attack
accuracy across all runs",
        "std_dev_run": 0.05,
        "ideal_range_description": "The ideal range of the accuracy score
(that represents perfect privacy)",
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            "minimum": 0.0,
            "maximum_description": "The maximum value of the ideal range",
            "maximum": 0.0
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    }
}
}
]
}
},
    "overall_privacy_health_description": "The overall privacy health scores resulting from
this assessment. The higher these scores are, the better the privacy of the assessed model .
All scores are between 0-1.",
    "overall_privacy_health": {
        "accuracy_health_score_description": "The overall privacy health score based on the
aggregated attack accuracy, normalized such that higher means better privacy.",
        "accuracy_health_score": 0.55,
        "precision_health_score_description": "The overall privacy health score based on the
aggregated attack precision, normalized such that higher means better privacy.",
        "precision_health_score": 0.12,
        "recall_health_score_description": "The overall privacy health score based on the
aggregated attack recall, normalized such that higher means better privacy.",

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    "recall_health_score": 0.18,
    "f1_health_score_description": "The overall privacy health score based on the
aggregated attack f1 score, normalized such that higher means better privacy.",
    "f1_health_score": 0.15
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  "producer_id": {
    "producer_description": "The name of the company that provided the tool (e.g.,
IBM)",
    "producer": "IBM",
    "name_description": "The name of the tool",
    "name": "Privacy Risk Evaluation Toolkit",
    "version_description": "The version of the tool",
    "version": "0.1.0"
  }
},
  "aggregate_score_description": "The overall privacy health score, based on the
accuracy_health_score and normalized to be between 0-100. The higher this score is, the better
the privacy of the assessed model.",
  "aggregate_score": 55.0
},
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    "summary": "Based on the assessment results, the following mitigations are
recommended.",
    "recommendations": [
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        "description": "Differential Privacy enables training ML models with a small amount
of noise such that the effect of any single sample on the resulting model is negligible.",
        "reason": "The assessment result shows a vulnerability to the Membership Inference attack
family.",
        "link": "https://application-
aip360.qbhuaxaorld.useast.codeengine.appdomain.cloud/tools#differential"
      }
    ]
  }
},
  "dimensions": [
    {
      "name_description": "The name of the dimension (e.g., privacy)",
      "name": "privacy",
      "context_description": "Additional information about the assessment of this dimension",
      "context": {

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"metrics": [
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    "attribute_inference_accuracy",
    "attribute_inference_precision",
    "attribute_inference_recall",
    "attribute_inference_f1"
],
    "thresholds_description": "Thresholds for each metric (minimum and maximum values
of the range of the metric), if relevant",
    "thresholds": [
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            "name": "membership_inference_accuracy",
            "value": [
                0.5,
                1.0
            ]
        }
    ],
    "advanced_description": "Additional information, if relevant",
    "advanced": [],
    "params_description": "Additional parameters to the metrics, if relevant",
"params": []
    }
}
]
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